

Statistical distances in 35 indigenous varieties of rice, U.P., India.

lowest for Budhiabanko and Sugarimohar, followed by Sukhdas and Churamani.

An examination of the percent contribution of each character to divergence showed grain yield as the major con-

tributor (77.8%) followed by days to maturity and days to heading. Plant height and spikelets per panicle contributed equally (1.8%) toward D^2 . Test weight contributed the least (0.5%) to D^2 . ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Rice tungro virus resistance in medium-duration prerelease cultivars

S. Srinivasan, Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai-612101, Tamil Nadu, India

Cultivars of all crops performing significantly better in yield and quality than

the existing cultivars are tested in adaptive trials in farmers' fields before release. During 1980, medium-duration cultivars TNAU 15776-3, AD6380, and DPI 591 were evaluated with three standard ones — Ponni, IR20, and M. Boothy — at 12 sites in Thanjavur district, Tamil Nadu.

Since its appearance in Thanjavur in

1978, tungro has been the primary disease in rice cultivation. The medium-duration cultivars raised in adaptive trials in the district were evaluated for their relative resistance to rice tungro virus. With the 12 sites as replications, the data on the rice tungro virus were statistically scrutinized (see table).

Mean incidence of rice tungro virus (RTV) at Thanjavur District, Tamil Nadu, India.

Culture	Parentage	RTV (%) ^a	
		AV	TV
DPI591	IR1712/IR1330	4.4	12.1
AD6380	IR8/Co25	5.1	13.1
M. Boothy	Tg65/ME80	12.5	20.7
Ponni	TG65/ME80	13.8	21.8
IR20	IR262/TKM6	65.4	54.0
TNAU15776-3	ASD5/IR20	89.1	70.7
C.D. = (P = 0.05)			6.3

^aAV = actual percentage of RTV worked out. TV = transformed value (angular value) for the actual percentage.

DPI 591 and AD6380 recorded a very low tungro incidence of about 5%. That indicated their high field resistance to the disease. If released as new varieties, the two cultivars can be best utilized in the rice tungro problem areas. ■

Resistance to bacterial blight

V. Mariappan, Valluva Paridasan, and P. Durairaj, Coimbatore, India

Rice cultivars were screened for resistance to bacterial blight disease. The plants were raised in pots containing wetland soil and in the field spaced 20 × 10 cm. Fertilizers were applied at 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha. The plants were inoculated at three stages: seedling (20 days), tillering (50 days), and boot-leaf. The disease severity was scored on a scale of 0-9. Many cultivars were rated susceptible; a few were moderately resistant.

Interestingly, ASD5 was resistant, comparable with TKM5 until tillering. IR22 and IR26 were moderately susceptible and ASD5 was resistant in the tillering stage. But ASD5 became infected in the panicle-emergence stage. Progeny of ASD5 — TNAU7124 and TNAU 15776 — also scored resistant until tillering and were moderately susceptible in the boot-leaf stage. The con-